

Effect of viscosity and pressure on a poor boy downhole gas separator under continuous gas-liquid flow

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ABSTRACT

Downhole gas separators are ubiquitous devices needed for the proper functioning of subsurface pumps. Contrasting its widespread use, the knowledge of its performance is quite limited. Among the various types of separators, the “poor boy” design stands as a simple, robust and easy to build device. These features have been appreciated in the oilfield during decades. Nevertheless, its performance is still not well understood. In this paper, progress on the research in static downhole gas separators are presented. A 3 ½-inch poor boy type gas separator was evaluated with a continuous gas-liquid flow resembling an above perforations downhole arrangement with a 7-inch production casing. Tests were carried out using an standard ISO 150 viscous oil and air in a large scale experimental facility. As was previously found with water and air, results with oil corroborate the existence of two separation efficiency regions. The first one is a high, nearly constant, efficiency zone for low liquid flow rates. The second zone, the efficiency is an almost linear function of the liquid flow rate. The main effect of a higher

viscosity is to increase the separation efficiency in a significant amount. Gas flow rate and pressure play a lesser role influencing the behavior of the separator. On the other hand, gas-liquid flow pattern arises as an important factor. An improved formula for the separation efficiency calculation based on dimensionless parameters is provided to be used for a wide range of conditions. This formula is suited for continuous flow downhole pumps such as progressing cavity pumps.

KEYWORDS

Artificial lift, downhole pumps, downhole gas separation, poor boy separator, two-phase flow.

INTRODUCTION

In general, downhole pumps such as progressing cavity, sucker-rod and centrifugal have a substantial multiphase handling capability. Nevertheless, in the case of positive displacement pumps, the gas that enters the pump chamber antagonizes with the liquid, spoiling the finite volume per revolution or

stroke length available for lifting liquid. Moreover, disruption of the pumping action may occur. For example, gas-lock in sucker-rod pumps and surging due to loss of liquid flow continuity in centrifugal pumps. Excessive gas volume has been identified as an important factor determining the run life of progressing cavity pumps (Ramos et al. 2008, Figuera et al. 2012, Díaz et al. 2014). In all these cases, the installation of a downhole gas separator is advantageous.

Static downhole gas separators, that is, with no moving parts, have been known and used for decades. Cylindrical reverse flow types such as the “poor boy” and Gilbert or “cups” design are very popular. Unfortunately, the performance of said separators is not well known. This is a serious matter. The lack of a set of rules or formulas to predict the downhole gas separation just adds another layer of uncertainty to the design of an artificial lift system. This knowledge vacuum has turn some production engineers wary or just plain distrustful of separators, specially when handling heavy oils.

The present article is an advance of a research project on poor boy downhole separators. This type of device is quite popular in Venezuelan oilfields, used in both sucker rod and progressing cavity pumping systems. A 3-inch full size separator in a 7-inch casing was tested at the Artificial Lift Laboratory of PDVSA Intevep. This research addresses the case of vertical wells where the pump intake is placed well above the producing interval.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Lea & Bearden (1982) investigated the effect of free gas on the performance of downhole centrifugal pumps. These authors described an “annulus separation effect”, which is essentially the primary separation that takes place in the annular space comprised

between the production casing and the separator housing. Two experimental conditions were found using water and air at pressures in the range of 25 to 30 psig that promoted the separation efficiency: a) the greater the gas volume present and b) the lower overall pumping rate, the greater the separation efficiency.

Podio et al. (1995) described a separator based on various improvements with respect to conventional separators: a) decentralization of the separator, b) placement of inlet ports in the narrower annular region and c) inducing the movement of gas bubbles toward the wider annular region. These improvements can be collectively associated as flow conditioning to get a better primary separation. Podio et al. also defined a “separation capacity”, being the maximum total gas and liquid flow rate at which the pump will be filled almost completely.

Robles (1996) divided the overall separation process into two stages: a) a first stage taking place at the annular space between the casing and the separator and b) a second stage occurring in the interior of the separator. The first stage was previously identified by Lea & Bearden (1982) as the annulus separation effect. The experimental technique described in Robles' work served as a basis for later researchers.

McCoy et al. (2005) used the experimental data published by Lisigurski (2004). In their analysis, these authors indicated the presence of a “zero gas flow boundary”, where the amount of gas entering the separator was negligible. The authors performed experiments with different types of separators, pointing out that most of the liquid enters the separator through the lower row of openings. Finally, the experiments indicated that the gas superficial velocity in the casing-separator annulus modified the separation efficiency.

Bohorquez et al. (2007) presented a further advance with respect McCoy et al. (2005)'s research. In this work, previous findings such as that entry port geometry does not appear to have a significant impact on the separator efficiency and that there exists a region of low liquid velocity in which the amount of gas that succeeds entering the separator is zero or insignificant were corroborated.

Ananaba (2007) compared the experimental results and visual observations obtained after changing the dip tube configuration from the conventional straight design to a helical design in static downhole gas separators. The separator designs were tested over a range between 0.8 and 6.0 m³/h of water and air rates between 13000 and 115000 scfd. The results showed that the evaluated static centrifugal separators induced centrifugal forces for gas liquid separation incorporating driving mechanisms that greatly improved overall separation efficiency. There are also results on bubble rise velocity experiments on a variety of liquids with viscosities between 1 and 3500 mPa s in a vertical wellbore annulus configuration.

Figuera et al (2012) evaluated static helical, horizontal (inflow V-shaped) and poor boy separators installed in 15 vertical and deviated wells producing extra-heavy oil. The results obtained were: a) 14% increment in production rate, b) pump's run life increase from 12 to 18 months, and c) increment of pumping efficiency from 30% to 40%. Poor boy separators showed the best efficiency with 55%, followed by the horizontal separator which exhibited 35% and the helical separator yielding 25%.

Ibarra et al. (2013) presented an experimental study of a poor boy downhole gas separator using air and water as working fluids. The present paper is a continuation of their research.

Díaz et al. (2014) discuss the importance of down-

hole gas handling in a extra-heavy oil field. After installing various in-house designed separators for progressing cavity pumps, they observed a measurable increase in casing gas flow.

Ibarra et al. (2014) made a comparison between poor boy and helical separators using a standard ISO 150 oil. They found helical separator's separation efficiency in the range of 30% to 50%, depending weakly on liquid flow rate. On the other hand, for the same flowing conditions, the poor boy performed substantially better, with a separation of 90% and up.

EXPERIMENTAL FACILITY

The experimental circuit is located at PDVSA Intevep's Artificial Lift Laboratory. A sketch of this circuit is show in Figure 1. The facility has a -inch casing where a downhole gas separator connected to a production tubing string can be placed to reproduce the actual geometry inside an oil well. A two-phase flow through this casing is established by a rotary pump and a screw air compressor. The maximum liquid flow rate is about 13 m³/h, depending on the fluid properties. The air mass flow rate can reach up to 2000 kg/h against a discharge pressure of 700 kPa.

The liquid mass flow rate is measured with a Coriolis flow meter. The air flow rate injected into the circuit is measured with an orifice plate. Both fluids merge at a tee junction at the bottom of the casing. This casing is 20 m tall. The top 8 m section is made of transparent acrylic tubes. The two-phase mixture travels upward through the casing where it finds the downhole separator under test. At this point, all the liquid and a certain amount of gas flow into the separator through its openings. The remaining gas continues its way up to the free surface and out of the casing. The fluids that entered the separator flow through a 3½-inch production pipe up to

the top of the casing. This mixture is discharged into a process separator where air is allowed to escape to the atmosphere while the liquid is sent back to pump inlet. The flow rate of both exiting air currents are measured with orifice meters. The casing hydrostatic pressure was kept stable by means of control valves that regulated the amount of air that was liberated to the atmosphere. The amount of air mass injected is controlled continuously to balance the amount of it that is removed from the circuit. Failure to keep the gas mass balance under check may lead to serious misleading results.

A sketch with dimensions of the tested separator is in Figure 2. This separator was taken directly from the field. It is build with standard oilfield piping. Dimensions in Figure 2 should suffice to reproduce this device in any workshop.

GAS SEPARATION TESTS AND DISCUSSION

Experimental tests of a poor boy separator with water (Ibarra et al. 2013) have shown that separation efficiency is a function of liquid flow rate, gas mass flow rate and gas density.

$$\frac{\dot{m}_{ag}}{\dot{m}_{ig}} = \eta = f(q_l, \dot{m}_{ig}, \rho_g) \quad (1)$$

Separation efficiency is the ratio of separated gas going through the annular space \dot{m}_{ag} and total gas mass flow rate \dot{m}_{ig} . The stronger parameter in Equation 1 is q_l , with \dot{m}_{ig} and ρ_g playing a secondary role. An increase in \dot{m}_{ig} improves marginally the efficiency and an increase in ρ_g goes the opposite way. The influence of these last variables seems to be related to gas-liquid flow pattern. Another relevant behavior is the existence of two efficiency regions. The transition zone is between 2 and 2.9 m³/h for water. For q_l less than 2 m³/h, efficiency is very high and quite constant, in the range

of 95% to 98%. For q_l larger than 2.9 m³/h, efficiency depends on the three variables in the right hand side of Equation 1. The existence of a high separation zone was already remarked by Podio et al. (1995).

A new set of data was collected using oil ISO 150 as liquid in order to study the effect of liquid viscosity on the separation process. This fluid has a dynamic viscosity of 132 mPa s at 40 °C. The values used in the experiments are in Table 1. The older water data set is in Table 2. A comparison of η between water and oil at constant separator's inlet pressure of about 480 kPa, $\rho_g = 5.8 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and $\dot{m}_{ig} = 46 \text{ kg/h}$ is in Figure 3. The efficiency exhibits the same trend as was already found with water. The constant η and variables regions are present. The constant η region is larger with oil, reaching up to 2.6 m³/h, while with water the onset of transition to variable efficiency is set around 2 m³/h. The authors were not able to gather reliable data for $q_l < 2.0 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ using water due to the difficulty to measure efficiencies close to 1 with $\dot{m}_{ig} = 46 \text{ kg/h}$, so no points are shown in Figure 3. The remarkable feature in this plot is the significant improvement of the separation process with the more viscous liquid. A possible cause for this fact may be found in bubble shape and dynamics. In Figure 4 there are pictures of quite close flowing conditions for water and oil. The two-phase flow pattern is different for each fluid. The gas flow in picture *a* is distributed into small spherical bubbles flowing in a churn-like pattern. A detailed observation shows that the spherical bubbles are arranged into tight clusters that move as if they were a single large bubble, but without merging. On the other hand, the flow in picture *b* contains two distinct bubble shape populations. There are small gas bubbles with a tendency to flow upwards with a more or less rectilinear motion, exception made to those bubbles pulled by liquid flow

into the separator, and very large gas bubbles that succeed in passing by the separator and escape rather unshaken to the free surface. These bubbles are known as Taylor bubbles. They expand up to fill the annular radius and embrace partially the separator's housing, always leaning against a preferential side of the annular space, even for a concentric annular. Images of these bubbles can be seen in Viana et al. (2001).

The gas-liquid flow pattern observed in viscous flow seems to promote gas separation, overcoming the increased drag force on bubbles of a more viscous fluid. Thus, it is relevant to know the flow pattern near the separator in order to understand the separation process.

DIMENSIONLESS PARAMETERS AND REGRESSION FORMULA

The physical quantities associated to the separation process are: a) mass flow rates: liquid \dot{m}_l , total gas \dot{m}_{tg} and separated or annular gas \dot{m}_{ag} , b) physical properties of the fluids: liquid density ρ_l , gas density ρ_g , liquid viscosity μ_l , gas viscosity μ_g , surface tension σ , c) the length scale is the hydraulic diameter defined between the well casing and separator housing, that is $d_h = d_c - d_s$ and d) gravitational acceleration g . This set of variables gives rise to 7 dimensionless parameters, one of them is separation efficiency in Equation 1. The remaining parameters are:

Liquid Reynolds number:

$$R_l = \frac{\dot{m}_l}{d_h \mu_l} \quad (2)$$

Total gas Reynolds number:

$$R_{tg} = \frac{\dot{m}_{tg}}{d_h \mu_g} \quad (3)$$

Eötvös number:

$$Eo = \frac{d_h^2 g \rho_l}{\sigma} \quad (4)$$

Morton number:

$$M = \frac{\mu_l^4 g}{\rho_l \sigma^3} \quad (5)$$

Ohnesorge number:

$$Oh = \frac{\mu_l}{\sqrt{\rho_l d_h \sigma}} \quad (6)$$

Density ratio:

$$\rho^* = \frac{\rho_l}{\rho_g} \quad (7)$$

Liquid Reynolds number is the primary parameter because the liquid motion is the responsible for gas being swallowed into the separator. Total gas Reynolds number competes with R_l for flowing space and thus, contributes to the flow field agitation and the characteristics of the two-phase flow pattern. Eötvös and Morton numbers are mandatory in the description of bubble motion. Density ratio is needed to close the set and is a consequence of the two phase flow. It is noted that fluid pressure actually translates into gas density. In this study, Ohnesorge and Morton numbers are coupled, because no change in d_h was made. So, Oh is disregarded for the remaining of the analysis.

Previous works (Ibarra et al. 2013, 2014) have shown that η is a strong data collapsing dimensionless parameter. In Figures 5 and 6 are plots of η vs. R_l for the complete water and oil data sets, respectively. There are two operation regions: high constant separation efficiency and variable as a function of R_l . The border between these regions depends on R_l and fluid properties. The separation is in the range 98% to 99% for water with $R_l \leq 7200$

and oil with $R_l \leq 18$. For both fluids, η is mostly governed by R_l , exhibiting a fairly linear relationship. The dispersion Figures 5 and 6 is explained by the other dimensionless parameters and the associated experimental variability. This scatter is more pronounced with oil due the difficulty to precisely control the hydraulic circuit at high liquid flow rates.

Figures 7 and 8 show a logarithmic transformation (base 10) of η vs. R_l for water and oil, suggesting a linear relationship between $\log \eta$ and R_l . A linear regression is applied to fit the variable efficiency data set using 6 dimensionless parameters and the linear model:

$$\log \eta = a_0 + a_1 R_l + a_2 R_g + a_3 R_g^2 + a_4 \rho^* + a_5 Eo + a_6 \log M \quad (8)$$

The coefficients are in Table 3.

In Figure 9 is a plot of measured vs. predicted efficiencies values using Equation 8. The mean relative error is 1% based on data-fitted value differences and 6% based on absolute differences.

The separator depicted in Figure 2 together with Equation 8 provides a simple gas separation technique for downhole pumps, even for small free gas content, light or extraheavy oil. Furthermore, wellbore inclination should improve η due to flow pattern stratification. Results presented here also serve as a benchmark for other separator design.

CONCLUSIONS

Extensive laboratory tests of a 3 1/2-inch poor boy separator was done regarding its separation performance under a wide range of flowing conditions. It was found that this device has two separation regimes : a) high efficiency with values in the range of 95%-98% and b) efficiency depending on liquid Reynolds number.

Visualization of the two-phase flow using water and a more viscous fluid strongly suggests that flow pattern is a key factor affecting the separation process. Large viscosity values seems to promote the formation of large bubbles and an enhancement of separation. Eötvös and Morton numbers are used to take this into account. More research has to be done on this aspect to understand the flow dynamics. Also, changing the annular space dimensions could yield valuable data.

Gas Reynolds number and fluid density ratio are secondary variables, but still influential.

The experimental results were condensed into a simple formula to be used in practical cases to estimate the amount of gas that will be ingested by a continuous flow downhole pump.

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NOMECLATURE

d_c , casing diameter, m

d_h , hydraulic diameter, m

d_s , separator diameter, m

\dot{m}_{ag} , annular gas mass flow rate, kg/s

\dot{m}_l , liquid mass flow rate, kg/s

\dot{m}_{tg} , total gas mass flow rate, kg/s

Eo , Eötvös number

M , Morton number
 Oh , Ohnesorge number
 R_g , gas Reynolds number
 R_l , liquid Reynolds number
 ρ_g , gas density, kg/m³
 ρ_l , liquid density, kg/m³
 ρ^* , density ratio
 μ_g , gas viscosity, Pa s
 μ_l , liquid viscosity, Pa s
 σ , surface tension, N/m
 η , separation efficiency

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Table 1: Oil an air data ranges.

Separator's inlet pressure (kPa)	Gas density (kg/m ³)	Liquid density (kg/m ³)	Liquid viscosity (mPa s)	Gas mass flow rate (kg/h)	Liquid flow rate (m ³ /h)	
					Min	Max
482	5.7	880	423	46	1.4	7.6
		881	472	199	1.5	7.8
		877	430	304	1.5	7.3
		876	516	369	1.7	8
657	7.9	880	483	45	1.5	9.8
		880	475	197	1.5	7.8
		876	475	298	1.5	9.7
		877	479	358	1.5	9.2

Table 2. Water and air data ranges.

Separator's inlet pressure (kPa)	Gas density (kg/m ³)	Gas mass flow rate (kg/h)	Liquid flow rate (m ³ /h)	
			Min	Max
241	2.9	4.0	1.9	10.8
		13.4	1.9	10.3
		22.7	0.6	10.2
		58.4	2.0	8.6
484	5.8	4.0	1.9	10.2
		8.0	2.0	10.2
		26.9	1.9	10.4
		45.7	2.1	11.1
		101.0	2.0	11.1

Table 3: Coefficients for Equation 8.

a_0	-1.4062E+00
a_1	-1.3716E-05
a_2	1.5508E-06
a_3	-1.5767E-11
a_4	1.7358E-04
a_5	1.0391E-03
a_6	-7.3069E-02

Figure 1: Downhole separation test loop diagram.

Figure 2: Poor boy separator used in the tests.

Figure 3: Combined η vs. q_l for water and oil data, $\rho=5.8 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and $m_{ig}=46 \text{ kg/h}$.

*Distributed spherical
bubble swarms*

a

Large gas bubbles

b

Figure 4: Flow patterns are different for water and oil. White rings in “b” are inlet holes.

a) Water, $q_l=2.0\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $\dot{m}_{ig}=7.9\text{ kg/h}$ and $\rho_g=5.8\text{ kg/m}^3$

b) Oil, $q_l=2.2\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, $\dot{m}_{ig}=8.5\text{ kg/h}$ and $\rho_g=5.8\text{ kg/m}^3$.

Figure 5: η vs. R_l for water data.

Figure 6: η vs. R_l for oil data.

Figure 7: $\log \eta$ vs. R_l for water data.

Figure 8: $\log \eta$ vs. R_l for oil data

Figure 9: Efficiency data vs. fitted model in Equation 8 with $\pm 20\%$ error boundaries.